

Studies on the Proton Magnetic Resonance Spectra of Bisaryl Isopropyl Phosphonates

EUGENE SEBASTIAN J. NIDIRY* and N. K. ROY

Division of Agricultural Chemicals, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi-110 012

Manuscript received 11 October 1988, accepted 2 February 1989

Analysis of the proton magnetic resonance data of twenty bisaryl isopropyl phosphonates showed that electron-withdrawing groups on the phenyl ring cause downfield shift of both alpha- and beta-protons on the alkyl side chain. Electron-withdrawing groups on the phenyl ring were also found to enhance the coupling constant between beta-protons and phosphorus.

THE proton magnetic resonance spectra of organo-phosphorus compounds present an extra facet of interest and information in that the phosphorus-31 nucleus has a spin of 1/2 and so are capable of splitting the signals of proximate protons of the molecule. In the earlier investigations¹⁻⁴ on the pmr spectra of many organophosphorus compounds including some phosphonates it was observed that phosphorus-31 causes splitting of the signals of protons attached to the saturated carbon, alpha or beta to the phosphorus, but in no case the splitting is observed for more remote protons. It was also observed that electronegativity of phosphorus causes downfield shift and enhances the coupling constant of alpha-protons. A systematic study on the effect of electronegativity of phosphorus on the chemical shift of beta-protons does not appear in literature. *O,O*-Bisaryl isopropyl phosphonates⁵, recently reported by us, contain both alpha- and beta-protons and the analysis of pmr spectra of the compounds is reported here.

Experimental

Synthesis of phosphonates: The compounds were synthesised by the condensation of various phenols with isopropyl phosphonic dichloride, which in turn was prepared by the reported method⁶. Details regarding the synthesis, purification and structural confirmation are described elsewhere⁵.

Pmr spectra: These were obtained on a Varian EM-360 (60 MHz) instrument using TMS as internal standard. The solvent used for compounds 1-19 was CCl₄ and that for 20 was CDCl₃.

Results and Discussion

The ¹H chemical shifts and coupling constants of various protons are presented in Table 1. The

most characteristic feature of the pmr spectra was the presence of a double doublet corresponding to the six beta-protons on the two terminal methyl groups, arising out of strong spin-spin coupling of the beta-protons with phosphorus and the vicinal proton. It was present in the spectra of all the twenty compounds; additionally methyl groups present in the aromatic part showed their own part.

The alpha-proton is also coupled with the vicinal protons as well as with the phosphorus nucleus giving a multiplet. The multiplet was too complex to calculate the coupling constant with beta-protons or with phosphorus. Also when methyl groups are present on the phenyl rings, these protons interfere with the peak corresponding to the alpha-proton making it difficult to determine the chemical shifts in most cases. However, those chemical shifts which could be determined, at least approximately, are presented in Table 1.

Comparison of the chemical shift values (Table 1) shows that there is a downfield shift when electron-withdrawing groups are attached to the phenyl rings. This downfield shift is seen in the cases of both alpha- and beta-protons. Also when electron-withdrawing group is at the *ortho*-position, the downfield shift is enhanced over the compound having substituent at the *para*-position.

An attempt was made to quantitatively correlate the chemical shifts of beta-protons with electronic effects of the substituents with the phenyl ring. Hammett's electronic parameter⁷ for individual compounds ($\Sigma\sigma$) was calculated by simple additivity principle, taking values of σ_p and σ_m from literature⁸. For *ortho*-substituents, σ_p along with Swain - Lupton constant, *F* for proximity polar effect suggested by Fujita and Nishioka⁹ was taken. The Swain - Lupton constant is designated as *F*(S.L.) in order to

*Present address: Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Hessaraghatta, Bangalore-560 089.

TABLE 1—PMR DATA OF BISARYL ISOPROPYL PHOSPHONATES WITH ELECTRONIC PARAMETERS

Compd. no.	R	Chemical shifts (δ)				Coupling constant (Hz) $J_{PCCH\beta}$	Hammett's parameter ($\Sigma\sigma$)	Proximity parameter ΣF (S.L.)
		ArH	OH $^{\alpha}$	OH $^{\beta}$	Other protons			
1	H	7.10	2.20	1.35	—	19.5	0.00	0.00
2	2-Cl	7.30	2.30	1.45	—	20.5	0.23	0.41
3	4-Cl	7.15	2.25	1.35	—	19.5	0.23	0.00
4	2-OCH $_3$	7.10	2.30	1.40	3.70(2-OCH $_3$)	19.5	-0.27	0.26
5	4-OCH $_3$	7.10	2.20	1.35	4.30(4-OCH $_3$)	19.5	-0.27	0.00
6	2-OH $_2$	7.05	ND	1.35	2.20(2-OH $_2$)	19.5	-0.17	-0.04
7	3-OH $_2$	7.10	ND	1.35	2.30(3-OH $_2$)	19.5	-0.07	0.00
8	4-OH $_2$	7.00	ND	1.35	2.30(4-OH $_2$)	19.5	-0.17	0.00
9	2-NO $_2$	7.65	2.45	1.45	—	21.0	0.78	0.67
10	4-NO $_2$	8.00	2.45	1.40	—	20.0	0.78	0.00
11	4-O(OH $_2$) $_2$	7.15	ND	1.35	1.30(4-O(OH $_2$) $_2$)	19.5	-0.20	0.00
12	4-SO $_3$ H $_2$	7.10	ND	1.35	2.40(4-SO $_3$ H $_2$)	19.5	0.00	0.00
13	2,3-(OH $_2$) $_2$	6.90	ND	1.35	2.10(2-OH $_2$) 2.20(3-OH $_2$)	19.0	-0.34	-0.04
14	2,4-(OH $_2$) $_2$	6.90	ND	1.35	2.10(2-OH $_2$) 2.20(3-OH $_2$)	19.0	-0.34	-0.04
15	2,5-(OH $_2$) $_2$	6.85	ND	1.35	2.20(2-OH $_2$) 2.30(3-OH $_2$)	19.0	-0.24	0.00
16	3,4-(OH $_2$) $_2$	6.85	ND	1.35	2.25(3-OH $_2$) 4-OH $_2$)	19.0	-0.24	0.00
17	3,5-(OH $_2$) $_2$	6.80	ND	1.35	2.25(3-OH $_2$) 5-OH $_2$)	19.0	-0.14	0.00
18	2,3,5-(OH $_2$) $_2$	6.80	ND	1.35	2.10(2-OH $_2$) 2.25(3-OH $_2$) 5-OH $_2$)	19.0	-0.14	0.00
19	2,4,5-Cl $_3$	7.50	2.25	1.45	—	21.0	0.83	0.41
20	Cl $_3$	—	2.50	1.60	—	21.5	1.43	0.82

*ND=not determined.

avoid confusion with significance index F . The following regression equations were obtained,

$$\delta_{CH\beta} = 1.37 + 0.11 \Sigma\sigma \quad (1)$$

$$n=20, R=0.87, F=55.98$$

$$\delta_{CH\beta} = 1.35 + 0.23 \Sigma F(S.L.) \quad (2)$$

$$n=23, R=0.94, F=130.94$$

Consideration of both the parameters gave the following multiple linear regression equation,

$$\delta_{CH\beta} = 1.36 + 0.04 \Sigma\sigma + 0.17 F(S.L.) \quad (3)$$

$$n=20, R=0.96, F=96.45$$

In the above equations, n is the number of compounds considered, R the correlation coefficient and F the significance index with respect to the equation. F values of equations (1)–(3) show significance at 1% level. From Table¹⁰, $F_{(1,19)}=8.29$ is significant at 1% level and $F_{(2,17)}=6.11$ is significant at 1% level; and equation (3) explains 92% of the variation in chemical shifts exhibited by the members of the series.

Comparison of the coupling constants of beta-protons ($J_{PCCH\beta}$) shows that they are enhanced when electron-withdrawing substituents are with

the phenyl ring (Table 1). Here also the effect of *ortho*-substituents is more than that of *para*-substituents.

Regression analysis of the coupling constant ($J_{PCCH\beta}$) with Hammett's electronic parameter ($\Sigma\sigma$) and Swain–Lupton constant resulted in the following equations,

$$J_{PCCH\beta} = 19.53 + 1.43 \Sigma\sigma \quad (4)$$

$$n=20, R=0.90, F=78.98$$

$$J_{PCCH\beta} = 19.32 + 2.73 \Sigma F(S.L.) \quad (5)$$

$$n=20, R=0.895, F=72.45$$

Consideration of both the parameters together gave the multiple regression equation,

$$J_{PCCH\beta} = 19.41 + 0.82 \Sigma\sigma + 1.47 \Sigma F(S.L.) \quad (6)$$

$$n=20, R=0.95, F=74.49$$

The F values of equations (4)–(6) show significance at 1% level¹⁰. Equation (6) explains 90% of the variation in coupling constant exhibited by the members of the series.

The enhanced coupling constant with electron-withdrawing groups can be explained by the theory proposed by Hendrickson *et al.*² to explain similar phenomenon in the case of alpha-protons.

The sigma-electron contact contribution to the spin-spin coupling constant between two nuclei is considered to be directly proportional to the product of electron densities of the two bonding orbitals through which they interact at their respective nuclei. For covalently bonded hydrogen, the contribution is considered essentially the same as that for hydrogen in the $1s$ state, but for atoms with hybridised bonding orbitals the contact contribution is proportional to the percent s -character in the hybridised orbitals used in forming the bond. The hybridisation of phosphorus will, however, depend on the relative electronegativities of substituents. s -Orbital of an atom tends to concentrate in the hybrid orbitals that are directed to less electronegative groups. Thus electron-withdrawing groups lead to placing positive charge on the phosphorus atom and also serve to direct s -character into orbitals of phosphorus directed towards less electronegative isopropyl group. When s -character of P-C bond is enhanced, the contribution towards spin-spin coupling with beta-protons is also enhanced.

This is perhaps the first report on the effect of electronegativity of phosphorus on the coupling constant of beta-protons.

The coupling constant between alpha- and beta-protons ($J_{CH\alpha CH\beta}$) was different in the two halves of

of the spectra. The low field half of the spectra of beta-protons gave a coupling constant of 6 Hz and the high field half of the spectra gave a coupling constant of 7 Hz similar to the observation made by Siddall and Prohaska¹ in the case of isopropyl phosphonic dichloride. However, this coupling constant ($J_{CH\alpha CH\beta}$) was not in any way influenced by the substituents present on the phenyl ring.

References

1. T. H. SIDDALL and C. A. PROHASKA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 2502.
2. J. B. HENDRICKSON, M. L. MADDOK, J. J. SIMS and H. D. KAESZ, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 449.
3. H. R. HUDSON, R. G. REES and J. E. WEEKER, *J. Chem., Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1974, 982.
4. L. M. JACKMAN and S. STERNHELL, "Applications of NMR Spectroscopy in Organic Compounds", Pergamon, New York, 1972, pp. 353-356.
5. E. S. J. NIDIRY and N. K. ROY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 1024.
6. A. M. KINNEAR and E. A. PERREN, *J. Chem. Soc. (II)*, 1952, 3437.
7. H. H. JAFFE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, **53**, 191.
8. C. HANSCH and A. LEO, "Substituent Constants for Correlation Analysis in Chemistry and Biology", Wiley, New York, 1979, p. 49.
9. T. FUJITA and T. NISHIOKA, *Prog. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1976, **12**, 49.
10. S. P. GUPTA, "Statistical Methods", Sultan Chand and Sons, New Delhi, 1986, p. 38.